
The Earth: A Lost Planet from another Universe

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ABSTRACT: There are several competing theories about the ultimate fate of the universe and possibility of anything preceding the Big Bang, while other physicists and philosophers refuse to speculate, doubting that information about prior states will ever be accessible. Some scientist have suggested various multiverse hypotheses, in which our universe might be one among many universes that likewise exist. There has been so many possibilities that are yet to be explored and investigated about our earth. The Earth is strangely different from other member of the universe. This study and observation intended to interpret the likelihood of our Earth been a stranger in a foreign universe.

KEYWORD: Universe, Earth, Planets, Solar, galaxy.

INTRODUCTION

It is generally known that the universe is all of space and time and their contents, including planets, stars, galaxies, and all other forms of matter and energy [1]. 'Our Universe' is believed to be about 13 billion years old [2,3] with a minimum diameter of 23 trillion light years, and approximately 93 billion light-years in diameter at the present day[4,5,6]. There are hundreds of billion galaxies in the universe with hundreds of billions of stars in our Milky Way. Many of the stars in a galaxy have planets. At the largest scale, galaxies are distributed uniformly and the same in all directions, meaning that the universe has neither an edge nor a center. Our planet, the earth, is no more than a small point in a universe full of worlds [7,8].

The Earth is part of a unique planetary system, under the milky way galaxy align with different matter and energy [9, 10, 11]. Earth is the third planet from the Sun and the only astronomical object known to harbour and support life. According to radiometric dating estimation and other evidence, Earth is formed over 4.5 billion years ago. Within the first billion years of Earth's history, life appeared in the oceans and began to affect Earth's atmosphere and surface, leading to the proliferation of anaerobic and, later, aerobic organisms [13, 14, 15]. Some geological evidence has indicated that life may have arisen as early as 4.1 billion years ago. Since then, the combination of Earth's distance from the Sun, physical properties, and geological history have allowed life to evolve and thrive. In some other study, it is believed that in the history of life on Earth, biodiversity has gone through long periods of expansion, occasionally punctuated by mass extinctions. More than 99% of all species that ever lived on Earth are extinct [16, 17, 18, 19]. But what if these believe and estimation are not entirely true.

POSSIBLE TRUTH

A more holistic, philosophical and analytic look at the Earth shows that it may be a stranger among the universal bodies it found itself. A direct example is the fact that the makeup and composition of the Earth is destitutely different from other planetary features. Earth is unique among the known planets: it has an abundance of water. Other worlds — including a few moons — have atmospheres, ice, and even oceans, but only Earth has the right combination to sustain life. The Earth seems to be the only planet among other uncountable 'floating particles' that is habitable to all forms of life; animal, plants and microorganisms. It is unique among planets even in our solar system for having water in its liquid form at the surface, in an amount conducive to life sustaining and evolving. Earth's crust is made up of several elements: oxygen, 46.6 percent by weight; silicon, 27.7 percent; aluminum, 8.1 percent; iron, 5 percent; calcium, 3.6 percent; sodium, 2.8 percent, potassium, 2.6 percent, and magnesium, 2.1 percent [21, 22]. No other planet has close to this geologically and biologically unique blend. The Earth plate tectonics allows for the carbon-silicate cycle to operate over geological timescales. With the carbon-silicate cycle, the levels of carbon in the atmosphere get regulated to keep the surface temperature around that of liquid water. Oxygen is another vital element for life. Free in the air and dissolved in water, oxygen is second only to nitrogen in abundance among uncombined elements in the atmosphere. Plants and animals

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use oxygen to respire and return it to the air and water as carbon dioxide (CO₂) [23,24,25]. Also, Earth's atmosphere is composed of about 78 percent nitrogen, 21 percent oxygen, 0.9 percent argon, and 0.1 percent other gases. Trace amounts of carbon dioxide, methane, water vapor, and neon are some of the other gases that make up the remaining 0.1 percent [26, 27,28]. Such special atmospheric mix needed for a biological energy generation, growth and nucleation for all form of life cannot be found in any other other planet or body existing in our present universe. Another aspect of Earth is its proportionate size: If it was much smaller, it wouldn't be able to hold on to our precious atmosphere, but much larger and it might be a gas giant too hot for life.

It is possible that the Earth was part of another universe, with similar or closely related condition, system, matter and energy to that of ours. Earth may be originally located peripherally from its parent and may lack enough pull-in force (Oyepata Force) resulting in been pulled off by our currently strange universe that may possess a much stronger force (Antioyepata force). If this theory is true our planet may not be at the center of our current universe, rather it may have been comfortable trapped, sustained or stabilized by the combination of force it posses and by the force around it.

Another plausible theory is the reinterpretation of big bang theory. Every universe is sustained by a balance of two forces centripetal (Oyepata force) and centrifugal (Antioyepata) force. It is possible that at a point or time our parent Universe (Opeyemi Universe), for some yet to be known reasons had a chronic or acute drop in Oyepata force, compared to an incredibly strong Antioyepata force. This failed balance may have resulted in total or peripheral explosion of Opeyemi's Universe causing different fragments and matter to be snatched away by multitudes of available universe. This may explain why it is very difficult to find another Earth-like planet in our current universe (called Dare's Universe). The big bang theory (in this case Simeon Oyepata's theory) may not be the beginning of a (the) Universe, rather the end of our previous Universe. It is also possible that our parent or Opeyemi's Universe to be well over 13 billion years. This may be the reason for chronic decay, disintegration and/or explosion. These theories may explain why many unnatural cycles that we assumed to be natural continuously occur. These include

1. Adaptation and survival of the fittest. It is worthy of note that from the period of our planet leaving Opeyemi's Universe to its current fate in Dare's Universe, most organisms and microorganism have undergone adaptive change or regrettably gone extinct.
2. Death and Reproduction; it is possible that our Opeyemi's Universe (parent Universe) contains fundamental elements that provides close to eternal existence, that is, the ability for humans to live at least a thousand years. But because of absence or loss of this life sustainable element due to unfavourable universe condition, living organism, humans in particular, may have underwent rapid evolutionary changes that favours rapid reproduction to compensate for short life and death.
3. Sickness and diseases: the origin of sickness and diseases maybe due to inconveniences the change caused living organisms of different forms resulting in different form of disease manifestation. It is also possible that struggle for survival and inadvertent mutation and evolutionary changes may have resulted in some microorganisms relying on other organism for survival, in the process, causing infection and diseases on the host

CONCLUSION

The fact that Earth hosts not just different forms of life, but also intelligent life. It makes it doubly unique. It is possible that some other ostracized or snatched away planets by our current or other universes may have lost many of their parental trace due to harsher environment, hence becoming inhabitable. It is important we find and explore all possible explanation on the origin of the Earth. It is also vital we locate our original planetary, solar and galaxy neighbors or even Universe. In that way, the Earth can be at peace with itself and we the inhabitant will understand and appreciate that we are the true alien.

Ethics declaration

Competing interests: The author declares no competing interests.

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